

[4+2] Cycloaddition reaction : Synthesis and antifungal activities of 2-substituted 1,2,4-triazolo[3,2-c][1,3,5]thiadiazine-3,3-dioxides

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Manuscript received online 06 August 2012, revised 09 August 2012, accepted 16 August 2012

Abstract : 3-Benzylideneamino-1,2,4-triazole undergoes [4+2] cycloaddition reaction with sulfene resulting in good yield of [1,2,4]-triazolo[3,2-c][1,3,5]-thiadiazine-3,3-dioxide derivatives. The title compounds have been screened for their antifungal activities.

Keywords : [4+2] Cycloaddition reaction, sulfene, 1,3,5-thiadiazine dioxides, antifungal activities.

Introduction

Fused 1,2,4-triazole represent an interesting class of compounds due to their versatile biological activities and their synthesis has attracted the attention of several synthetic groups¹. Sometimes the fusion of heterocyclic nuclei enhances the biological profile manifold more than its parent nucleus². A variety of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives have been described for their biological activities including antidepressive, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal and insecticidal properties³. The 1,3,5-thiadiazine and its derivatives are reported to be insecticidal and acaricidal activity⁴⁻⁹. These compounds are also reported to possess antifungal^{10,11}, hypopemic¹² and antiatherosclerotic activity¹³. The triazolo-thiadiazines are reported to be antimicrobial, antibacterial, anticancer¹⁴ and diuretic activity¹⁵. These diverse biological activity prompted us to synthesise some [1,2,4]-triazolo[3,2-c][1,3,5]-thiadiazine-3,3-dioxide derivatives with the expectation of enhancing the biological activities of these class of compounds. The title compounds were synthesized from 3-benzylideneamino-[1,2,4]-triazole¹⁶ and sulfene generated *in situ*, by a [4+2] cycloaddition reaction and screened these compounds for their antifungal activities.

Results and discussion

The heterodiene Diels-Alder cycloaddition reaction is

a most versatile routes for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds^{17,18}. It has been observed that [4+2] cycloaddition reaction involving sulfene is very rare¹⁹. Sulfenes have received little attention to date as dienophiles^{20,21}. The suitable use of diene and dienophiles determines the wide range of cycloadducts. 3-Benzylideneamino[1,2,4]-triazoles (**2**) are important and versatile intermediates in organic synthesis and they have been prepared by refluxing a mixture of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole and appropriate aryl aldehyde in presence of few drops of piperidine for 10 h (Table 1). The structures of **2** were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass) data. The IR spectra (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) of **2a-g** exhibited bands near 1630 and 1590 cm⁻¹ attributed to exocyclic and cyclic C=N respectively. The ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) due to the -N=CH- protons for the compounds **2a-g** appeared at δ 8.68 to 8.90 ppm. Multiplets for aromatic protons appeared in the region δ 6.25 to 7.82 ppm and also for C-5 proton. The mass spectrum of compound **2a** showed a stable molecular ion peak at 172 (M⁺, 100%) corresponding to its molecular weight.

[1,2,4]-Triazolo-[3,2-c][1,3,5]-thiadiazine-3,3-dioxide **3** were synthesized by the dropwise addition of methanesulfonyl chloride in dioxane to a solution of 3-

Table 1. Physical data of 3-benzylideneamino-[1,2,4]-triazole (2a-g)

Compd.	R ¹	Yield	M.p.
		(%)	(°C)
2a	H	80	240
2b	4-NO ₂	85	170
2c	4-OCH ₃	90	250
2d	4-Cl	80	190
2e	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	85	296
2f	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	70	161
2g	2-OH	70	210
3a	H	72	172
3b	4-NO ₂	85	110
3c	4-OCH ₃	76	135
3d	4-Cl	80	126
3e	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	86	154
3f	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	75	112
3g	2-OH	83	160

benzylideneamino[1,2,4]-triazole in dioxane at 0-5 °C (Scheme 1).

The structures of the products have been assigned **3** on the basis of analytical and spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass) data. The IR spectra of **3** showed characteristic SO₂ stretching frequency around 1170 and 1370 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra (in CDCl₃, δ ppm) of **3** showed singlet at δ 3.20 to 3.50 ppm due to methylene protons (-CH₂-) at C-7 and δ 3.65 to 3.90 ppm for methine protons at C-5 and at δ 8.05-8.16 ppm due to NH protons. Mass spectra of **3a** showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 250 (M⁺, 15%). In view of these observations the structure of the compound **3** were proposed to be [1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,2-*c*][1,3,5]-thiadiazine-3,3-dioxides.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in an oil heated Buchi ap-

Table 2. Analytical and spectral data for compounds 2a-g

Compd.	Molecular formula	Found (Required) (%)			IR (KBr, ν cm ⁻¹)	δ _H (CDCl ₃ -DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆) for 2a-g δ _H (CDCl ₃) for 3a-g
		C	H	N		
2a	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄	62.59 (62.79)	4.51 (4.65)	32.40 (32.56)	1630, 1590 (C=N), 3420 (NH)	6.21-7.54 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.10 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.70 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2b	C ₉ H ₇ N ₅ O ₂	49.60 (49.77)	3.15 (3.23)	32.12 (32.26)	1625, 1588 (C=N), 3400 (NH)	6.45-7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.00 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.75 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2c	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	59.50 (59.41)	5.02 (4.95)	27.61 (27.72)	1633, 1595 (C=N), 3400 (NH)	3.25 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 6.72-7.78 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.90 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2d	C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ Cl	52.47 (52.30)	3.32 (3.39)	26.95 (27.12)	1625, 1595 (C=N), 3400 (NH)	6.46-7.48 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.72 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2e	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅	61.58 (61.40)	6.19 (6.05)	32.90 (32.76)	1630, 1596 (C=N), 3425 (NH)	3.12 (6H, s, -NMe ₂), 6.12-7.75 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.08 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.68 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2f	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	55.03 (54.79)	5.20 (5.02)	25.52 (25.57)	1628, 1582 (C=N), 3415 (NH), 3410 (OH)	3.73 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 5.91 (1H, s, -OH), 6.51-7.72 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.88 (1H, s, =NCH-)
2g	C ₉ H ₈ N ₄ O	57.34 (57.45)	4.12 (4.26)	29.62 (29.79)	1635, 1590 (C=N), 3405 (NH), 3420 (OH)	5.50 (1H, s, -OH), 6.65-7.60 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.10 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 8.92 (1H, s, =NCH-)
3a	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	47.84 (48.00)	4.12 (4.00)	22.10 (22.40)	1170, 1372 (SO ₂), 3410 (NH)	3.20 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.40 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 6.50-7.84 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.10 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)

Table-2 (contd.)

3b	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄ S	40.40 (40.68)	2.87 (3.05)	24.05 (23.90)	1176, 1375 (SO ₂), 3430 (NH)	3.26 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.48 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 6.62–8.00 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)
3c	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	47.30 (47.14)	4.54 (4.30)	19.76 (20.00)	1174, 1374 (SO ₂), 3420 (NH)	3.24 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.41 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 3.71 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 6.65–7.78 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)
3d	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	41.92 (42.17)	3.36 (3.16)	20.02 (19.68)	1172, 1370 (SO ₂), 3410 (NH)	3.22 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.40 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 6.52–7.90 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)
3e	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S	49.36 (49.15)	4.86 (5.12)	24.10 (23.89)	1178, 1374 (SO ₂), 3420 (NH)	2.82 (6H, s, -NMe ₂), 3.25 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.50 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 6.48–7.74 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)
3f	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	44.20 (44.59)	3.84 (4.05)	19.12 (18.92)	1172, 1370 (SO ₂), 3425 (NH), 3410 (OH)	3.26 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.50 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 3.62 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 5.60 (1H, s, -OH), 6.50–8.10 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)
3g	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	45.32 (45.11)	4.02 (3.76)	21.10 (21.05)	1170, 1372 (SO ₂), 3420 (NH), 3412 (OH)	3.24 (2H, s, -CH ₂ -, C ₇ -H), 3.44 (1H, s, C ₅ -H), 5.75 (1H, s, -OH), 6.40–7.85 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.10 (1H, s, C ₂ -H)

Scheme 1

paratus and were uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237-B and Perkin-Elmer system 2000 FTIR spectrometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX-90 (90 MHz) NMR spectrometer with TMS as internal reference. The mass spectra of the compounds were taken on a Finnigan MAT INCOS 50 GC/MS or Jeol D-300 instrument. C, H, N analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240 analyser. The purity of the compounds were checked by TLC.

Preparation of 3-benzylideneamino[1,2,4]-triazole (2a) : A mixture of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.42 g, 0.005 mol) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (0.53 g, 0.005 mol) were taken in a round bottom flask. To this mixture

25 ml of 2-propanol and 3 drops of piperidine was added and the mixture refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated in vacuum to dryness and the residue obtained was recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 240 °C, yield 80%, *m/z* 172 (M⁺).

Preparation of 2-phenyl-[1,2,4]-triazolo[3,2-c][1,3,5]-thiadiazine-3,3-dioxide (3a) : In a typical experiment, to a solution of 3-benzylideneamino[1,2,4]-triazole (2a) (0.344 g, 0.002 mol) in dry 1,4-dioxane (20 ml), triethylamine (0.56 ml, 0.004 mol) was added followed by methane sulfonylchloride (0.23 ml, 0.003 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (15 ml) drop by drop at 0–5 °C under stirring during 30 min. The stirring was continued for a period of 3–4 h at the same temperature. The reaction mixture was then

poured into ice (100 g) and extracted with chloroform (2 × 40 ml), and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure and recrystallization of the residue gave the compound **3a**, yield 82%, m.p. 172 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹): 1170 and 1370 cm⁻¹ for SO₂ stretching frequency; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 3.20 (2H, s, -CH₂-, C₇-H), 3.40 (1H, s, C₅-H), 6.50–7.84 (5H, m, Ar-H and C₂-H), 8.10 (1H, s, C₂-H); *m/z* 250 (M⁺).

Biological activity screening :

Due to diverse and interesting biological activities of 1,2,4-thiadiazine ring system, we screened these compounds for their antifungal activities against *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Drechslera oryzae*, two fungal pathogens causing diseases on agriculturally important food crops. The antifungal activities were evaluated according to the inhibition zone technique²². The compounds **3b**, **3d** and **3f** were found to be more effective at a concentration of 1 mg/ml. The control (without treatment) sets of experiments with both the fungal pathogens exhibited no inhibition of growth. However, the standard fungicide (carbendazim) showed 98.56 and 98.26% inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Drechslera oryzae* respectively at the same concentration of 1 mg/ml.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director, NEIST, Jorhat for the facilities provided to carry out the research work, also Mr. Pabitra Kumar Kalita, Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, Arya Vidyapeeth College, Guwahati, Assam for his useful suggestions during the research work.

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